

Seek and You Shall Find - Or Not! Why Can't We Find the Research Software We Really Need?

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Abstract: The abstract goes here.

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1 Introduction

Research software is a fundamental part of today's research, as a tool, as a result, or as an object of study itself. And the use and with it the importance of software for research will continue to increase in the future. As a digital artifact, software, like data, has become an integral part of research, which is why it is essential to treat it sustainably. To make the research process transparent and reproducible, software should be FAIR [CKB⁺21], i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The F in FAIR stands for findability, for example. Findability requires that "software and the associated metadata are easy to find for both humans and machines." [CKB⁺21] Specifically, this means that the software is assigned a persistent identifier (PID) and described with extensive metadata that is searchable and indexable (and FAIR itself).

However, FAIR metadata is only a necessary prerequisite for software to be found with as little effort as possible, if at all. If we look at the systems that researchers use to search for software, they have a variety of infrastructures at their disposal in which to search: a general purpose search engine is often the starting point for a search for software. Popular code repositories such as GitHub¹ make software available and also provide search functionality. Software repositories for different programming languages (e.g. python: pypi²; or R: CRAN³) or operating systems (e.g. Android: play store⁴; or the Debian package archive⁵) offer a development-centered approach for the former and a target system-oriented approach for the latter. Software is also published and can be found on publication platforms, with Zenodo⁶ being a prominent example.

These are just a few examples of the wealth of search options that researchers can use when searching for software and which we will discuss in more detail in this article. The bottom line

¹ <https://www.github.com>

² <https://pypi.org/>

³ <https://cran.r-project.org/https://cran.r-project.org/>

⁴ <https://play.google.com>

⁵ <https://packages.debian.org/index>

⁶ <https://www.zenodo.org>

is that software is scattered over several locations which increases complexity of the discovery process. To help researchers choose the right search option for their search for research software, we want to list the individual discovery pathways in this article and compare them on the basis of defined search and discovery relevant criteria. From this, we derive recommendations on how best to use currently available options and how infrastructures, some of which still need to be developed, should be built to optimally support the search for research software.

In section [Retrieval needs](#) (2) we will outline typical user types for the search for research software (2.1). Based on the user types, we will then identify scenarios that trigger a search for research software (2.2). Types and scenarios will in turn be used to develop criteria for evaluating the individual search options (2.3). These criteria are used for the subsequent evaluation of the individual pathways (??) which are introduced beforehand in section (3). In the following discussion (??), we address the fact that software can be searched and found in many places, that the facing possibilities in many pathways can be improved, and that the hosting or responsibility for the pathway itself lies in the hands of very different institutions. We draw conclusions from the field of data search. Finally, we address the differences between software search and software discovery and draw lessons for the search process.

2 Retrieval needs

2.1 Research software discoverers - categorization of user types

To facilitate discovery of research software, it is important to consider the contexts in which such discovery might be taking place or be attempted, particularly by whom, with which prerequisites and for what purposes. A common framework to describe and communicate such user-centric parameters of a technical system is that of a *persona*, i.e. a fictional characters described in terms of some characteristics deemed relevant for the system at hand [AP10]. The persona approach has been used in a variety of settings (e.g. HCI [PG03], healthcare [JVS17], and education [MOd15]), yet we are not aware of examples focused on research software discovery.

In this section, we will thus outline some personas we deem relevant for discovering research software. They differ in parameters that can be roughly grouped as **academic** and **technical** dimensions of the discovery of research software. Academic parameters would be the disciplinary background, the career stage, actual position and the institutional context. Technical parameters describe the persona's expertise in terms of using, running, building, designing, maintaining or documenting software and for which hardware.

Charly: PhD Student in Humanities This is a humanities PhD student with no programming experience who also does not need software development skills for their research. They want to automate simple analysis steps such as annotation and stylometry to speed up their research process. They are accustomed to intuitive user interfaces and are looking for user-friendly tools that simplify routine procedures without extensive configuration requirements. They want to manage and analyze their data efficiently. They rely on academic publications and peer recommendations when selecting digital tools. Their research questions are exclusively qualitative in nature and can usually be answered using a few software applications. The ideal discovery

system would explain tool functionalities and provide examples of how they can be applied in humanities research.

Sascha: PostDoc in BioStatistics This researcher is an early-career scientist in the field of biostatistics with advanced R programming skills who frequently performs quantitative analyses. They are proficient in the R ecosystem and proactively seek new R packages to expand their statistical method set, improve his workflows, and respond to new questions in his current project. Their main objective is to identify and use software tools to analyse complex biological data. They care about efficiency, accuracy, and reliability of research software and are willing to spent time learning new tools. They frequently search CRAN, GitHub, and Bioconductor repositories for relevant tools. They value the ability to integrate tools into existing R-based pipelines and therefore prefer modular, interoperable solutions. They can also contribute to software projects by reporting problems, suggesting improvements or submitting patches. The discovery system should support filtering by statistical methods, dependencies and version history.

Zhu: Research Software Engineer (RSE) Here we have a research software engineer who creates and maintains software applications for research projects. They have practical programming skills, but did not receive intensive programming training at university. They are familiar with certain programming languages (Python, R, JavaScript) and tools used in their research area, but may not be aware of alternative solutions. They seek software that is robust, well-maintained, and compliant with FAIR principles. Their search is driven by functional requirements, performance considerations, licensing constraints, maintainability and extensibility. They are interested in both general-purpose software and domain-specific tools. The RSE also contributes to open source projects. The discovery system should provide technical metadata, version control history and user feedback on software stability.

Kim: Experienced Developer Entering a New Field This user is an experienced software developer with a background in computer science but no experience in the scientific field. They have exceptional programming skills in languages such as Java, C++ or Python, but are new to the research area with its specific tools and methods. They have been tasked with developing new research software and needs an overview of relevant software tools in this area. As Linux users, they are accustomed to working with command line interfaces and scripting languages. Their main goal is to quickly acquire knowledge of the research software landscape and identify suitable tools for their project. They value comprehensive documentation, tutorials and community support for research software. The discovery system should provide insights into software popularity, typical use cases, and recommended learning resources for domain newcomers.

Andrea: Data Librarian Cataloging Research Software This is a data librarian who supports researchers in finding and accessing relevant software tools and resources. They also play a crucial role in cataloging and documenting software developed by researchers within her institution, which is essential for research reporting and end-of-year impact assessment. They have a strong understanding of research workflows and data management, as well as information

Dimension	Charly PhD-Stud	Sascha PostDoc	Zhu RSE	Paul Dev	Martin Lib
Academic	**	****	***	*	**
Technical	*	**	***	****	**

Note: * no prior experience, ** beginner, *** advanced, **** expert

Table 1: Dimensional Skill Sets of the Five Personas for Research Software Discovery

literacy. Their main objective is to provide researchers with advice and recommendations on research software while assessing usability, accessibility, and discoverability of research software and regularly evaluate new tools and resources. They evaluate software based on institutional policies and compliance with open science or FAIR principles. The discovery system should provide well-structured metadata, citation formats, and cross-referencing with repositories such as Zenodo or institutional archives.

2.2 Scenarios for searching research software

The personas presented in Section 2.1 have different reasons for searching for software. In this section, we show various scenarios that can trigger a search for research software. Each individual scenario can be associated with one or more personas.

Solve Task. You have a task or a problem which is very tedious, repetitive, or complex. There should be an easier, more efficient to solve this – ideally semi-automatically. However, you don't know what tools exist or how to formulate your problem as keywords or queries.

Compare software. You want to compare software that solve the same problem. Likely, one is best fit to your specific case. But there is no comparison of properties like performance, features, ease of use, compatibility, or community support.

Develop software. You want to develop new software and make sure you're not reinventing the wheel. By building on existing solutions, you can make sure not to duplicate effort and focus on novel work. It is complicated to make sure all relevant software is on your radar, especially where even known tools have potentially little known, disclosed or simply talked about features.

Feature missing. You have a tool that's almost perfect, but it is missing a specific feature. It might be possible to compensate using a different tool, but you are unaware if any other tool solves this task. Even if there was, it is questionable how you could find out if it would be compatible with your workflow.

Add features. You have developed a software that's perfect and that makes you suspicious you might be missing something. You want to find similar software to see what features and

compatibilities they cover. Other than some forum threads and short related work sections, this information is hard to come by.

Measure impact. You have developed a software and need to measure the impact of your tool. While some citations are picked up by search engines, many more likely use your software without mentioning it. There is little to no indication how many downloaded, (re-)used or derived your work.

Review software. You review software available online as part of your security assessment. You appreciate open source software, especially to ensure adherence to best practices or certain standards in quality or reliability. Even if you have identified an issue, your options are limited in publicizing them, especially when you want to reach all third party users of this software.

Reproduce results. You need to reproduce results found in a paper using a (specific) software. In theory, you just follow their description and referenced software stack. In practice, the often rather brief and incomplete descriptions are usually not sufficient to identify versions, niche steps, applications and settings. Difficulties identifying and accessing software are also caused by insufficient citation practices as well as link rot.

Write paper. You write a paper and need to know what other tools exist for the related work section. You don't care for extensive details, just need a reliable list to check for yourself that you're not missing any major players. Those short, but solid lists are hard to come by.

Describe software. You want to describe a software for your paper and make sure to cover all important information. While you have used this tool for a while, you are always only using it for a specific problem. To properly describe it in a cohesive background section, your surface level understanding is not enough.

Review Literature. You conduct a literature review on what software is relevant to your research question. While you extract these from scientific article mentions, you think there should be a better way for this. Sadly, authors rarely link or even reference every tool they used inside papers and the metadata is limited and heterogeneous.

Add to catalog. You want to add a software to a catalog and need more information about it. Your ontology and description fields are well-defined, but the software not so much. Despite the software still being in use, it is especially hard to come by details due to the main developer leaving the project.

2.3 Evaluation criteria for discovery pathways

Based on the persona and their characteristics defined in the previous sections, as well as on the various scenarios for the search for research software, we now derive evaluation criteria for the retrieval pathways which we present in section 3. Furthermore, we cross-checked, refined and

Scenario	Charly PhD-Stud	Sascha PostDoc	Zhu RSE	Kim Dev	Andrea Lib
Solve task	X	X	X	X	X
Compare Software		X	X	X	X
Develop Software		X	X	X	
Feature Missing		X	X	X	
Add Features		X	X	X	
Measure Impact		X	X	X	(X)
Review Software			X	X	
Reproduce Results	X	X	X		
Write Paper	X	X	X	X	
Describe Software	X	X	X	X	
Review Literature	X	X	X		
Add to Catalog		X	X	X	X

Table 2: Summary of existing use-cases and matching persona from section 2.1

added to our criteria using existing evaluation criteria for similar services, such as repositories [Con22] or library discovery systems [CY14]. The resulting list of criteria is summarized in table 3.

3 Retrieval pathways

Researchers have a fairly extensive number of systems at their disposal in which they can search for research software. In this section, we introduce various retrieval options available to researchers. An overview of all options can be found in table 4. Each of these options is then briefly introduced.

3.1 Code repositories

Code repositories are public platforms that host code and offer management and collaborative functions. The search functions vary and are rather basic, for example they can contain filters for programming language, license, category or deployment options. These platforms facilitate contribution and reuse. Popular examples are GitHub⁷, GitLab⁸, Codeberg⁹, Bitbucket¹⁰, SourceForge¹¹.

⁷ <https://github.com>

⁸ <https://gitlab.com>

⁹ <https://codeberg.org/>

¹⁰ <https://bitbucket.org/>

¹¹ <https://sourceforge.net/>

Criteria	Short Description	Measurement unit
Quantity	Amount of available software items in the pathway	Absolute count (number)
Filter options	Available filters to refine search results	Count + List of filter types
Host institution	Organization maintaining the pathway	Categorical (e.g., Private company, research institution)
PIDs		
Documentation	User documentation of the pathway and the search functionality	
Ease of use		
Funding		
Usage Statistics		
Scope		
Scientific domain	Pathway focus on specific scientific domains	Categorical (single or multiple domains)
Publication types	Types of content available in the pathway	Categorical (Software only, data, text)
User Engagement		
Content	Opportunities for users to contribute content	Categorical (None, comments, reviews, tagging, editing)
Administration	Opportunities for users to manage the pathway	Categorical (None, moderation, governance roles)
APIs	Availability of programmatic access to the pathway	Categorical (None, REST API, OAI-PMH, GraphQL)
Metadata Schema	Standardized metadata structure used for software description	Categorical (None, Dublin Core, Schema.org, custom)
Recommender	Recommendation service for related software items	Categorical (None, keyword-based, AI-based, collaborative filtering)
Search Functionality	Search capabilities provided by the pathway	Categorical (Basic, Advanced, Full-text)
Community Size	Number of active users engaging with the pathway	Absolute count (number of users)
Integration with Other Platforms	Ability to connect with repositories/databases	Categorical (None, Zenodo, GitHub, others)
Science Information		

Table 3: Criteria for the Evaluation of Pathways for Retrieval of Research Software

Search Paths	Code	Application	Metadata
Code Repositories	X		X
Mixed Content Publication Platforms	X		X
Software Repositories			
Programming Language Centered		X	X
Operating System Centered		X	X
Software archives	X	X	X
Catalogs			
Domain Specific			X
Institutional			X
National or Supranational			X
Curated Lists			
Search Engines			
General purpose search engines			X
Specialised search engines			X
Federated search engine			X
Software Journals			X
Knowledge Graphs			X
Social Networks			X
Large Language Models	X	X	X

Table 4: Summary of Existing Search Paths.

discovery paths	code	application	metadata
Software citation			
Software reviews			

Table 5: Summary of existing discovery paths

3.2 Mixed Content Publication Platforms

Researchers can use mixed content publishing platforms to publish their research results. Research results can be texts, presentations, posters, reports, research data, but also research software. Zenodo¹² is probably the best known example of a mixed content platform that provides various research results including code. Institutional repositories, which often provide mainly texts but also software, are also considered mixed content publishing platforms.

3.3 Software Repositories

Software repositories often also referred to as package repositories are central storage locations for software packages for a specific environment or ecosystem. We distinguish between software repositories for programming languages and repositories for a specific operating system.

¹² <https://www.zenodo.org>

Programming language centered repositories For many of the common programming languages, there is a central repository in which software developed in the programming language is stored and curated (e.g. PyPi for Python¹³, CRAN for R¹⁴, or crates.io for Rust¹⁵). Often a Package manager is offered around the software repository, which simplifies the search and installation of software packages as well as the handling of dependencies (e.g. pip for Python¹⁶, Cargo for Rust¹⁷, or Cabal for Haskell¹⁸).

Operating system centered repositories Similar to programming language centered repositories, there are central repositories for many common operating systems that store and curate software that is offered for the respective operating system. Each of the major Linux distributions has one or several central repositories as well as one or more package managers that make it easier to search for and install packages and manage dependencies (e.g. Debian based systems rely on APT¹⁹, pacman for Arch based systems²⁰, or DNF for Red Hat based systems²¹). FlatPak²² and Snap²³ are popular examples for linux distribution agnostic package delivery. HomeBrew²⁴ is a popular package manager for macOS while it can also be used under Linux. Conda²⁵ in turn is a popular package manager, known from the Anaconda distribution popular among data scientists, which is both operating system and programming language agnostic. The app stores and the underlying software repositories of mobile operating systems also fall into this category (e.g. the App Store of iOS²⁶, as well as for Android the Play Store²⁷ or the free and open source package manager F-Droid²⁸).

3.4 Software archives

Software archives preserve code for future generations. Software Heritage²⁹ is an academically funded initiative to collect and index source code [DC20]. They are archiving 31 different code management platforms, from which 27 are regularly crawled while 4 of them are being crawled on demand. 3 code hosting platforms do not exist anymore while the code is archived for future access on Software Heritage³⁰. In addition to the disappearance of single code hosting platforms

¹³ <https://pypi.org/>

¹⁴ <https://cran.r-project.org>

¹⁵ <https://crates.io/>

¹⁶ <https://pip.pypa.io/>

¹⁷ <https://doc.rust-lang.org/stable/cargo/>

¹⁸ <http://www.haskell.org/cabal>

¹⁹ <https://wiki.debian.org/AptCLI>

²⁰ https://archlinux.org/packages/core/x86_64/pacman/

²¹ <https://rpm-software-management.github.io/>

²² <https://flatpak.org/>

²³ <https://snapcraft.io/>

²⁴ <https://brew.sh/>

²⁵ <https://conda.io/>

²⁶ <https://appstore.com/>

²⁷ <https://play.google.com/>

²⁸ <https://f-droid.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

³⁰ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/#content>

such as Gitorious, Google Code or Bitbucket, the repositories of individual software projects can also be deduplicated or deleted. Software archives prevent this loss of software code and enable future access to software code to understand and reproduce research carried out with it.

3.5 Catalogs

While there are code management and publication platforms, there are also efforts to make research software better known and findable. Catalogs are an established concept to collect meta-data and point to (a persistent) location elsewhere. Such catalogs are often hosted and sometimes even curated by different institutions to ensure their long-term availability and high quality of entries.

Based on different use cases for the use of a catalog, we distinguish three basic subtypes of catalogs for research software: domain-specific, institutional, and national/supranational catalogs.

Domain specific Domain-specific catalogs focus on software that is used in a specific research domain. We find, for example, catalogs for domains like biology³¹, physics³², mathematics³³, humanities³⁴, astrophysics³⁵ or social sciences³⁶. The catalog of swMATH, for example, collects URLs to mathematical software and accompanying text publications. Users benefit from pointers to related software and also (software) citation information as an indicator for its popularity.

Institutional Institutional catalogs, on the other hand, list software developed by members of the respective institution. The Research Software Directory (RSD) of the Helmholtz Association³⁷ or the RSD of the eScience Center of the Netherlands³⁸ are examples of institutional research software catalogs.

National or supranational The acquisition of software can also take place at a national or even supranational level. For example, for Germany and its national research data infrastructure, NFDI.software³⁹ will be launched. NFDI.software is a basic service of the BASE4NFDI consortium, which aims to become a central marketplace to improve access to NFDI research software.

³¹ <https://bio.tools>

³² <https://physics.tools/>

³³ <https://www.swmath.org>

³⁴ <https://tapor.ca/tools>

³⁵ <https://ascl.net/>

³⁶ <https://www.sosciso.de>

³⁷ <https://helmholtz.software>

³⁸ <https://research-software-directory.org/>

³⁹ <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/nfdi-software>

3.6 Curated lists

Curated lists are collections of particularly high-quality content on a specific topic. The best known of these lists are the awesome lists on GitHub⁴⁰. Curated lists are very similar to catalogs, but often contain less metadata, if any. They are curated by individuals, institutions or communities. The content ranges from lists on every conceivable programming language, computer science, big data, testing, domain-specific ones⁴¹, a list about research software registries⁴², lists about general research software engineering⁴³ and many more.

3.7 Search engines

General purpose search engines follow broad content aggregation strategies and offer a general search UI. Different approaches to search technology developed over the decades. A common approach is to crawl/harvest resources, building a local index with normalized metadata and offering fast search functionality. Examples are WWW search engines like “Google” or science focused competitors like “BASE”⁴⁴. The term ‘meta search’ is sometimes utilized to differentiate this approach from, for example, ‘federated’ or ‘live’ search. There, a user initiates an instant search on several remote platforms, often enabled via API calls. An example for a federated search engine dedicated to research software is “Betty’s ReSearch Engine”⁴⁵ [SRW24].

3.7.1 General purpose search engines

3.7.2 Specialised search engines

3.7.3 Federated search engine

3.8 Software journals

Journals specializing in software publish text articles on software publications. Since scientific communication about research results is mainly in text form, the recognition and reward system is also based on a text-based publication infrastructure, e.g. journals and book publishers. Software journals use the scientific reward system to write about software and make the software visible and discoverable. JORS⁴⁶, JOSS⁴⁷ and IPOL⁴⁸ are community initiatives whereas SoftwareX⁴⁹ is an example for a publishing house jumping on the bandwagon of research software papers.

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/sindresorhus/awesome>

⁴¹ e.g. <https://dh-tech.github.io/awesome-digital-humanities/>

⁴² <https://github.com/NLeSC/awesome-research-software-registries>

⁴³ e.g. <https://github.com/hifis-net/awesome-rse>

⁴⁴ <https://base-search.net/Search/Results?lookfor=doctype%253A6>

⁴⁵ <https://gitlab.com/tuc-isse/public/betty-research-engine/>

⁴⁶ <https://openresearchsoftware.metajnl.com/>

⁴⁷ <https://joss.theoj.org/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ipol.im/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/softwarex>

3.9 Knowledge graphs

Knowledge graphs (KGs) offer a robust pathway for identifying research software tailored for specific research purposes as they organize and interlink diverse information in a structured manner. KGs represent fine-grained semantic descriptions of entities such as software, researchers, institutions, and research topics as nodes, with edges depicting the relationships between them. This structured approach facilitates semantic search capabilities, allowing researchers to find software related to specific topics even if not explicitly mentioned in descriptions. By navigating the graph, researchers can explore various relationships to discover relevant software, such as starting with a researcher in their field and tracing the software they have developed or used. KGs can integrate data from multiple sources, including academic publications, software repositories, and research databases, providing a comprehensive search experience. They can also power recommendation systems by analyzing graph structures and relationships, suggesting software that aligns with research interests. Additionally, KGs offer contextual information about software, aiding in evaluating its relevance and credibility. Advanced querying capabilities using languages like SPARQL or Cypher enable complex searches for software meeting specific criteria. Visualization tools further enhance the exploration process, offering an intuitive way to understand relationships and identify relevant software. By capturing collaborative networks, knowledge graphs facilitate connections with other researchers using the same tools, fostering potential collaborations. The dynamic nature of these graphs ensures they remain up-to-date with the latest software tools and research developments, making them an invaluable resource for researchers seeking to enhance their work with the most suitable software solutions.

3.10 Social networks

Perhaps not the most obvious option for finding research software, but a surprisingly common one, is the social network of a researcher. In interview studies about software discovery, participants often mentioned their academic network as a source of information about relevant research software [HG16, Gey20]. Possible ways of accessing knowledge in the social network are usually direct contact with colleagues, contact via institutional or domain-specific mailing lists, internet forums or web-based social networks.

3.11 Large Language Models

Large language models (LLMs) are a class of artificial intelligence systems that have been trained on vast amounts of text data to understand and generate human-like language. These models can be used for a wide range of tasks, including natural language processing, text generation, and machine translation. LLMs can be also applied for searching research software by identifying relevant software tools and providing information about their features and capabilities.

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